

Jede Stimme zählt

Developed by: polyspektiv Burgdörfer & Ness & Systainchange

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Competition, Constitutional Politics, Cooperation, Political Science, Rhetoric

Figure 1. Photograph of the game *Jede Stimme zählt* (*Every Vote Counts*) showing the box and game components. Image used for educational review; rights remain with the creators.

Introduction

Jede Stimme zählt (*Every Vote Counts*; see Figure 1) is a game about facts, values, topics, and processes within an election campaign, where players develop a political campaign. They must complete creative tasks and convince fellow players with their own ideas. In addition, they must demonstrate their competence by answering quiz questions.

The game conveys how an election campaign works. The biographies of political supporters provide insight into the diversity of political participation and encourage players to engage in their own political involvement.

The game includes both competitive and cooperative elements and can be used in a variety of ways. Target groups include university students, school pupils, and people interested in politics. Depending on the group, topics can be addressed at different levels of depth.

The first edition of Every Vote Counts was developed for the 2021 German federal election; since then, updated versions have been created for state elections and the 2024 European election. The game was developed in cooperation between Polyspektiv and Systainchange.

Facts

Release date:	01.09.2021
Developer:	Polyspektiv Burgdörfer & Ness & Systainchange
Game type:	Analog, Hybrid
Number of players:	6–24, optimal: 8–16
Format:	Synchronous
Time frame:	1.5–4 hours, optimal: 2.5–4 hours (larger groups require slightly more time than smaller groups)
Languages:	German
Environment:	For large groups: a room with 4–5 tables; for small groups: one table with 6–8 seats. No digital requirements when played analogue; for hybrid/digital play: 4–5 devices and stable Wi-Fi.
Material:	Paper and pens; video instructions: https://jedestimmezaehlt.de/film/
Price:	36.50€ for the physical game; for digital/hybrid use, arrangements must be made with the authors.

Resonance & Criticism

The game uses an innovative concept combining creative tasks with quiz challenges. Nearly 1,000 copies have been sold, reaching an estimated 15,000 people. Additionally, the game has been used in around 25 workshops focused on reflecting on elections and democracy (as of 10/2025).

Feedback from participants is consistently positive. Various aspects are highlighted: variety, use of different talents (creativity, knowledge, speed), freedom of playstyle (cooperative or competitive), accessibility, and the strengthening of political knowledge.

One challenge is the game's time intensity. It can only be modified to fit under 1.5 hours—for example, as a pure quiz game or as a cooperative format focused on gradually building and presenting a campaign.

Game principle & Process

The game is played in three to four teams, each consisting of two to six players. The goal is to collect as many supporters as possible for one's campaign. Smaller groups sit together at one table. For larger groups, one table in the middle holds all materials, while each team has its own table. The game materials include a game board and a round counter, plus several types of cards: supporter cards in four categories, collected throughout the game, and topic, task, and inspiration cards used explicitly in the creative rounds.

The two types of rounds—creative rounds and quiz rounds—alternate. In creative rounds, players develop their campaign: theme, party name, slogan, posters, campaign videos, etc. Teams complete these tasks simultaneously within a limited time, then present and evaluate each other's results. Teams may choose to cooperate or compete.

In quiz rounds, teams encounter potential supporters represented on cards. To win them, they must answer a question. Each round, they choose one of four political fields (political system, political content, media and public communication, networks and party work) and attempt to answer a question correctly.

If the team answers correctly, it receives the supporter card. Some cards announce events instead of asking questions. Social interactions within teams are essential in both round types. Interactions between teams, mainly through mutual evaluations, also play a significant role in game dynamics. Players may adopt a wide variety of political positions, advocate for them, and justify them. The only requirement: campaigns must be conducted using democratic means. Ideally, the instructor is familiar with the game beforehand so they can introduce the different elements step by step.

Learning objectives & Educational fields of application

The game pursues several central learning and training objectives. First, it engages players with political topics and campaign processes by simulating how an election campaign works and how a political campaign is built step by step. In creative rounds, players develop their own campaigns and observe how others evaluate them, while quiz rounds introduce factual knowledge about the political system, democratic values, political debates, media use and public relations, interest groups, and party structures.

In addition, the game supports the practice of democratic attitudes and procedures. Players learn to communicate their views and argue for their interests, while becoming sensitized to the importance of listening and respectful interaction in the context of a fair election campaign. They also practice providing reasoned evaluations of political contributions.

The game further encourages political participation. By developing playful solutions to political issues and defending them, players often grow unconsciously into the role of someone who may wish to advocate for these ideas in real life. The biographies presented on

supporter cards strengthen awareness of the diversity of political engagement and encourage real-world participation.

Beyond political content, the game strengthens creative campaign skills. Players experience how a campaign is developed, from problem analysis and ideation to the creation of visual and textual elements and marketing strategies. These skills extend beyond political contexts and support general campaign competence.

Finally, the game promotes the development of cooperative and competitive strategies. Players experience how cooperative or competitive behavior influences others and the overall game dynamic, learning both to negotiate shared interests and to assert distinct positions in a competitive setting.

A teaching person is required to support the learning process by moderating gameplay, clarifying factual content, providing quality criteria, and ensuring real-world relevance during the debriefing phase.

Effectiveness

There are no scientific studies or evidence regarding the game's effectiveness. Feedback from workshops is consistently positive. Observations show that players find it motivating because different skills can lead to success. Points can be earned through knowledge, creativity, or social skills. The rapid alternation between round types suits the short attention spans of younger participants.

The creative solutions produced in the game can be broadly grouped into three categories: serious tasks with political content; humorous or silly solutions; and mixed solutions combining creativity, humor, and political content.

In-depth discussions on political positions, content, or participation are not part of the game itself, as they would slow down the fast, entertaining gameplay. In workshops, the game is supplemented with evaluation discussions, real-world transfer, and additional content to contextualize the session.

Potentially problematic aspects

The game contains time-bound information that must be updated regularly.

Special attention was given to diversity in the depiction of people. This representation reflects societal diversity (e.g., 50% women, 30% people with migration background, inclusion of people with disabilities) rather than the composition of political institutions (e.g., the Bundestag). In some contexts, this may irritate if it does not reflect the local perception of representation and is perceived as "forced diversity."

Reviewer(s): Saskia Sterzl

Sources

No external sources were used.